

DYNAMIC PERFORMANCE MODEL OF HYBRID POWER PLANT (WGS + GAS TURBINE)

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Abstract. *It is known that the role and importance of energy storage increases when operating a power plant based on a renewable energy source. This feature of the power plant operation is associated with the unevenness of electricity generation due to natural conditions. The paper assesses the performance of a hybrid power plant, namely, the degree of mutual influence is determined when operating a wind power plant and a gas turbine in a single system. The gas turbine is considered as a backup energy source, which is switched on in the absence of wind. Problems arising during the operation of a hybrid energy system consisting of wind power plants (WPP) and a thermal power plant (GTU) arise mainly due to the natural unpredictability of the wind power plants. A dynamic wind turbine model coupled with a power system model is needed to develop options for optimizing its performance in terms of efficiency, fuel consumption, and CO₂ emissions. The results illustrate the significant impact that dynamic performance modeling has on the design of a hybrid power system optimization and control system.*

Keywords: *Hybrid power system; wind power plant; gas turbine; CO₂ emissions; dynamic performance models; MATLAB/Simulink system.*

Introduction

The general wind turbine model is developed in Simulink and integrated with the power system model. The energy demand and wind speed are calculated to change over time, forcing the power system to operate under transient conditions. This provides additional information about the dynamic operation of the hybrid system and can also serve as a guide when designing a control system for this type of system.

Fig 1 Single line diagram of hybrid power plant

The expansion of wind power plants has transformed the gas turbines operation. The intermittent nature of wind prompts the gas turbines to operate with increased flexibility, for supporting their renewable plant partners and maintaining the stability of the electricity grid [1, 2]. Fast starts, shut downs and part load operation [3, 4, 5] are governing the operating profile of modern engines. It is vital, for an effective operation and maintenance (O&M) strategy, to employ tools and technologies that will support our understanding for these complex and nonlinear machines. Towards this end, gas turbine manufacturers have developed a suite of programs and systems that can model, monitor and analyse a plants performance [6]. Performance models of gas turbines play an important role [7, 8] in optimizing their operation. Recently, their transient behavior has attracted attention as they must operate in conjunction with renewable energy sources that are characterized by unpredictability in their operating schedule. Dynamic performance models of gas turbines can facilitate the design of control systems that will enable them to perform their complex new role [12]. From a maintenance perspective, dynamic models of gas turbines provide capabilities for condition monitoring, diagnostics [13, 14, 15, 16] and prognostication [17, 18]. A general wind turbine model is developed in Simulink and linked to the gas turbine model. The power demand and wind speed are designed to vary over time, forcing the gas turbine to operate under transient conditions. This scenario provides additional information about the dynamic behavior of the gas turbine and can also serve as a guide for designing a controller for hybrid plants. Finally, the performance of the hybrid plant is compared to that of a power plant operating on only two gas turbines to assess the shutdown capability of the gas turbines and their NO₂ emissions.

Mathematical model of a gas turbine

To develop a gas turbine model, the MATLAB/Simulink system was used [14]. The main components of a gas turbine are the compressor, combustion chamber and turbine. The exhaust gases from the gas turbine drive a free power turbine, which is connected to an electric generator, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Representation of the two-shaft engine model along with its station numbering [14].

Dynamic Simulation

The implementation method is based on the principle that fuel consumption imbalance occurs during a transient regime. Two combustion chamber volumes were added to the model, one before the turbine and one after the turbine, as shown in Figure 3. The component maps for the compressor, turbine, and power turbine are the same as in the steady state model.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the modular algorithm of the gas turbine transient model. [14].

The main parameters of the Gas Turbine used for the model are given in Table 1

Table 1

Symb	Parametr	Value	Unit
P ₁	Compressor discharge	147	kP
P ₂	Turbine exit	40	kP
N	Gas generator shaft	900	rp

Mathematical model of a wind turbine

Fig 4 Schematic diagram of a direct drive wind energy conversion system

A wind turbine converts wind energy into mechanical energy and then generates electrical energy through the operation of generators. According to aerodynamic analysis, the mechanical power P captured by a wind turbine from wind energy is:

$$P = 0.5 * \rho * A * v^3$$

$$v = \frac{(v_1 + v_2)}{2}$$

$$P_t = 0.5 \rho \pi R^2 v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta)$$

$$C_p = \frac{P_T}{P} = 0.5 * \left(1 - \frac{v_2^2}{v_1^2}\right) * \left(1 + \frac{v_2}{v_1}\right) \quad C_p \approx 0.593$$

where ρ is the air density, R is the radius of the wind wheel, v is the speed of the oncoming wind, and C_p is the power factor of the wind turbine, which is determined jointly by the ratio of the blade tip speeds λ and the inclination angle β .

A general wind turbine model available in MATLAB/Simulink [16] is used in this study to evaluate the performance of a hybrid power system when the wind farm is connected to the power grid.

The performance of a wind turbine is determined by the tilt angle β , the wind speed V_{wind} and the wind turbine speed N_{wt} . These are usually represented on a performance map as shown in Figure 3. The power output of a wind turbine, U_{wwt} , is given by [16]:

Figure 5 Wind turbine performance plot representing power output versus generator speed, for various wind speeds and blade angle $\beta = 0$ degrees.

The wind turbine model has three inputs namely β , V_{wind} , N_{wt} and one output U_{wwt} .

Figure 6. Block diagram of the hybrid gas/wind controller and optimization module [14].

It should be emphasized that the wind turbine used here is a general and simple model, which is consistent with the purpose of this paper.

Results

A hybrid power system consists of a gas turbine (power supply system) and a variable power wind plant. The total output power U_{Wtotal} of the hybrid power plant is given by

$$U_{Wtotal} = U_{Wgt} + U_{Wwt}$$

The lack of electricity ΔW created by wind turbines due to uneven wind flow is covered by the power supply system. This difference is expressed as follows:

$$\Delta U_W = D_w - U_{Wtotal}$$

At any time when demand is not met, the electrical system must respond by adjusting fuel consumption. An algebraic constraint is used to limit the difference to zero (i.e. $\Delta W = 0$) by adjusting the value of the fundamental electrical energy produced by the power supply system. The schematic diagram of the developed models is presented in Figure 7

Fig7 Block diagram of the hybrid control system and optimization module [14].

It should be emphasized that the wind turbine used here is a generic and simple model suitable for the purposes of this study.

The purpose of this case study is to evaluate the performance of a gas turbine when coupled to a wind farm. The calculated characteristics of the wind turbine are given in Table 2 and refer to the general wind turbine model.

Dynamic Performance model for Hybrid Power Plant

Table 2. Design characteristics of a wind turbine [14].

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Units
V_{wind}	Wind speed	12	m\sek
N_{gt}	Generator speed	1800	rpm
U W_{it}	Power output	1500	kWt

The hybrid power system shown in Figure 6 consists of a gas turbine and 14 wind turbines.

Figure 8. Diagram of a hybrid electrical system in Simulink [14].

The change in wind speed over time can be seen in Figure 9. This change is designed to assume that the power supply system will start operating near the design point. At the 2 and 5 o'clock mark, when the wind farm is producing a minimum amount of electricity, the power system will have to respond to this change by following demand according to the intermittent power output of the wind turbines.

Figure 9. Wind speed variation over time [14].

The required power of the consumer is from 28 MW to 37 MW. The above is combined with the changing wind speed, and the resulting output power of each system is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Schedule of operation of the power supply system and wind turbines to meet changing demand [14].

The output power varies over time, as can be seen in Figure 10, which shows the percentage of output power of each system. The wind farm provides up to 70% of the required power, and the maximum output power of the power supply system provides up to 75%.

Figure 11. The graph of the output power of the power supply system and wind turbines expressed as a percentage of the total power consumption over time [14]

The analysis of the operation graph of the power supply system and wind turbines to meet the changing demand (Fig. 11) shows that due to the wind speed fluctuation, the power supply system has to work at full power 65% percent of the time in the total 10-hour cycle. It is found that the characteristics of wind speed fluctuation, including frequency, amplitude and average value, have a great influence on the dynamic performance and power generation efficiency of the Hybrid Power System. This was confirmed by the simulation results. It should be noted that increasing the oscillation frequency will harm the dynamic performance and wind power generation of the wind turbine. On the contrary, increasing the oscillation amplitude and average wind speed will improve the wind power generation in the system to different degrees. These results are of great importance for the practical application and future research of the MPPT control strategy based on stochastic control.

Conclusion

In this chapter, a new gas turbine model is presented that aims to capture the nonlinear behavior of modern gas turbines. The model is built in MATLAB/Simulink. The Hybrid System Model combines an iterative approach with constant mass flow rate under steady-state conditions to initialize the state parameters in a dynamic model that uses the intercomponent volume method. The dynamic response of the model was evaluated for a hybrid gas-wind power plant consisting of 7 wind turbines. The result of this analysis shows the fast transient trajectories that the power system faces due to variable wind speed and fluctuating energy demand. In addition, the behavior of the hybrid power system highlighted the need for transient modeling since several operational issues need to be addressed to maintain stability in the grid.

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